

Geodynamic Model for the Formation of Neoproterozoic A-type Granites in the Western Yangtze Block

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ABSTRACT

Traditionally called the Jingning-Chengjiang period S-type granitic belt in the western margin of Yangtze Block may have formed by different tectonic evolutionary processes. The newly identified A-type granite in this granitic belt is a good diagnostic indicator of tectonic setting and provides insight into understanding these processes. We obtained zircon U-Pb age, elemental, and isotopic geochemistry data of granites from Shimian pluton, revealing that these traditionally thought S-type granites have A-type affinity. Furthermore, we conclude that Neoproterozoic Shimian A-type granite originated from the partial melting of a Mesoproterozoic juvenile felsic upper crust heating by the upwelling of asthenosphere through the slab window. The formation of Neoproterozoic A-type granites in the region is probably linked to an ancient ridge subduction.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous peraluminous granitic intrusions occur over a north–south distance of more than 700 km in the western Yangtze Block (WYB). These granites are traditionally called the Jining-Chengjiang period (Neoproterozoic) S-type granitic belt associated with W–Sn–Fe mineralization. Mabi et al. (2018), Mabi (2019) first obtained zircon U-Pb ages of 1055 ± 43 Ma and 1031 ± 77 Ma on Mosuoying pluton. Moreover, traditionally thought S-type Mianning pluton and Shimian pluton are identified as A-type granite (Huang et al., 2008; Mabi et al., 2023), leading to the question that this granitic belt may result from different tectonic events.

The Neoproterozoic granitoids cropping out in WYB had a great bearing on understanding the mantle nature, crustal evolution, and crust-mantle interaction of South China Craton (SCC) during the assembly and breakup of the supercontinent Rodinia. However, different geodynamic processes, predominated by the mantle-plume-related rift model and the

subduction-related arc model, are adopted to explain petrogenesis and tectonic implication of these granites and other predominant felsic rocks and minor mafic-ultramafic rocks in WYB.

Traditional thought Neoproterozoic S-type Shimian granitic pluton in the middle of WYB is confirmed to be A-type granite by carrying out detailed field studies and systematically measuring geological sections, combined with using geochemistry data including zircon U-Pb age, whole-rock major and trace elements, and isotopic compositions. This new find could be used as an indicator of tectonic setting to build a geodynamic model for explaining the formation of different types of Neoproterozoic rock with various chemical compositions in WYB.

2. METHODS

Zircon grains were separated and hand-picked. The U-Pb isotopic ratios were measured by Laser ablation ICPMS (GeoLas 250 LA and Agilent 7500a

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Fig. 1. (a) U-Pb concordia diagram of the studied granite sample; (b) Diagrams of $\epsilon_{\text{Hf}}(T)$ values vs. $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages for zircons from Shimian granites (Mabi et al., 2023).

Fig. 2. The multi-elemental spider diagram (a) and Chondrite-normalized REE patterns of Shimian A-type granites (Mabi et al., 2023).

ICPMS). Hf-isotope compositions of zircons were measured by using a Thermo Fisher Scientific Neptune Plus MC-ICPMS, obtaining the Hf-isotope compositions as illustrated in Fig. 1(b). The whole-rock major elements were determined by X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF; PW4400/40) and the trace elements were obtained by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS; XSERIESII).

3. RESULTS

Through the field observation, it is obvious that the Shimian pluton intrudes either the TTG gneisses of Kangding complex from which we obtained a U-Pb age of 772.4 ± 6.9 Ma (Mabi et al., 2024) or the Suxiong Formation which yielded a SHRIMP zircon U-Pb age of 803 ± 12 Ma (Li et al., 2002). It also can be seen that the Shimian pluton is unconformably overlain by the Triassic sandstone. U-Pb dating of a biotite monzogranite yield apparent $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages ranging from 576.77 ± 3.4 Ma to 789.7 ± 4.7 Ma. 7

spot analysis from oscillatory zoned cores, as shown in Fig. 1(a), yield a weighted mean $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ age of 728.5 ± 3.3 Ma. These 7 zircons showing oscillatory zoning have a Th/U ratio of above 0.6. Spot #9 is analysed on the structureless-core domain of zircon and yields a Th/U ratio of 0.3 and an apparent $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ age of 789.7 ± 4.7 Ma. In contrast, the zircons for spot #16 and spot #22 do not have a core-rim structure (Fig. 1), yielding the Th/U ratios of 0.8 and 0.06, respectively, and the apparent $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages of 576.7 ± 3.4 Ma and 576.8 ± 7 Ma. Therefore, 728.5 ± 3.3 Ma is recommended as the emplacement age of Shimian granite and the timing of the ~ 576 Ma is interpreted as the result of a metamorphic event in the region.

The granites display high contents of SiO_2 and K_2O , low CaO and Na_2O , with the characteristics of high silica, rich potassium, and low sodium. They are enriched in incompatible trace elements but depleted in Ba, Sr, P, Eu, and Ti (Fig. 2). Their A/CNK values range from 0.78 to 1.6, classified as weak per-

Fig. 3. Ridge subduction model of the western Yangtze Block. (a) plan view showing that two oceanic microplates separated by spreading ridge subduct beneath the South China Craton, and (b) a cross-sectional illustration of the slab window magmatism showing the hot asthenospheric mantle wells up in the gap created between the two diverging plates and provides the source of parental magmas of A-type granites (Mabi et al., 2023).

aluminous on A/CNK plot. They have high values of $10000 \times \text{Ga}/\text{Al}$ ranging from 2.63 to 6.53 and fall in the A-type field on both “Nb vs. $10000 \text{Ga}/\text{Al}$ ” and “Y vs. $10000 \text{Ga}/\text{Al}$ ” A-type granitoid discriminant diagrams (Whalen et al., 1987). In addition, they fall in the “within-plate” field of Pearce et al. (1984) and could be classified further as the A₂-subtype granite of Eby (1992), showing a crustal origin in the continent (Mabi et al., 2023).

Initial Hf-isotope ratios ($^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf}$)_i of Shimian granites range from 0.28232 to 0.28238. These zircons have positive, $\epsilon_{\text{Hf}}(t)$ of 0 to 1.7 (except one sample with -0.1), yielding two-stage Hf model ages ($T_{\text{DM}2}$) of 1206 to 1282 Ma (mean 1249 Ma) and T_{DM} ages of 1471 to 1601 Ma, respectively. We therefore propose a juvenile, 1.2 Ga Mesoproterozoic crustal source for the Shimian granites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It is generally accepted that the A-type granite can be formed from orogenic to anorogenic settings but is emplaced into a tensional environment either at the last stage of an orogenic cycle, or in the continental rift zone, or in oceanic basins. In addition, A₁-type and A₂-type granites are formed at the within-plate settings such as plumes, rift, and hot spots and the post-collision extensional settings including post-collisional extension, slab roll-back, and slab break-off, etc., respectively. In recent years, many cases of A-type granites formed by ridge subduction are documented, including numerous Cretaceous A₂-type granites in the Lower Yangtze River belt and Dabie orogenic belt in East China, the Mesozoic A-type granites in the Gondwana margin, the late Paleozoic A-type granites in Central Asian Orogenic Belt, the Cretaceous Chatham Rise A-type granites in the eastern Zealandia, and the Taitao granites in the Chile Ridge of South America (references in Mabi et al., 2023). Therefore, we proposed that the Shimian A-type granites were more plausibly generated in an extensional setting resulting from ridge subduction beneath WYB during Neoproterozoic era (Fig. 3).

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